

Abstract: yProvExplorer, a graph-based Science Gateway for enhancing user experience in navigating provenance data

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I. ABSTRACT

Data management and analysis have become increasingly complex over time. As these workflows evolve, the need for accurate data traceability becomes paramount. Without a clear record of who has made changes to the data, when and how, it becomes difficult to ensure its reliability and safe reuse. To address this issue, W3C introduced the PROV standard¹, a structured framework designed to capture the provenance of data. This standard helps documenting the entire lifecycle of data, from its origin to its end use, ensuring greater reliability and security. With PROV, every transformation or update can be traced back, improving transparency and reliability. PROV is definitely a key tool for improving data quality and facilitating informed reuse, making it easier to evaluate and trust the results of data-driven work.

Provenance files record the complete history of a dataset, tracing each step from its origin to its last modification. These files capture entities, activities, and agents involved in scientific workflows. Although the PROV model accurately documents the history of a data item, its practical use is often hampered by the lack of accessible and easy-to-use tools. Navigating the source files can be unintuitive and time-consuming, especially for those not used to it. This complexity reduces the potential for widespread adoption and integration of provenance data into everyday workflows. Many of the existing tools are too generic and lack advanced features tailored to the specific needs of provenance analysis. There is, therefore, a growing need for more user-friendly, purpose-built applications that can simplify the exploration of provenance data.

Among the available tools that support provenance standard, there are: 1) ProvStore²: a repository to store and manage PROV documents. 2) ProvToolbox³: a Java library for creating and converting PROV documents into different formats. 3) ProvJS⁴: a JavaScript implementation for managing PROV

data in the browser. 4) Prov Python⁵: an open source library for managing PROV documents in Python. 5) prov2neo⁶: a library for importing PROV documents into Neo4j for graph analysis. 6) Git2PROV⁷: a library for exporting provenance documents from Git repositories in the PROV format.

Our contribution fills the gap between existing libraries and services and an application designed to increase the final user experience.

To this end, we developed yProvExplorer⁸, a Science Gateway addressing the user's need of navigating through complex provenance documents, by providing a nicely arranged representation of all the interconnected provenance elements. All such elements are arranged in a two-dimensional space using a force-directed graph drawing algorithm⁹, provided by the library D3js¹⁰. The yProvExplorer consists of a self-contained web application implemented in React which can be easily deployed through Docker. It nicely integrates with the yProv ecosystem, therefore, allowing to load the documents directly from yProv storage service, in addition to open document directly from the local device. The tool guides the user in navigating the graph through links to the parent and child nodes, allowing to easily move toward the source data or toward the final data. The source code is available at <https://github.com/HPCI-Lab/yprov-explorer>.

¹W3C PROV overview <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

²ProvStore <https://openprovenance.org/>

³ProvToolbox <https://lucmoreau.github.io/ProvToolbox/>

⁴ProvJS <https://github.com/openprov/provjs>

⁵Prov Python <https://github.com/trungdong/prov>

⁶prov2neo <https://github.com/DLR-SC/prov2neo>

⁷Git2PROV <https://github.com/IDLabResearch/Git2PROV>

⁸yProvExplorer repository <https://github.com/HPCI-Lab/yprov-explorer>

⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Force-directed_graph_drawing

¹⁰D3 <https://d3js.org/>